

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

WORK RELATED RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Working space Health and safety is a shared responsibility between employer and employee. Acting as an employer, entity is required under the law to create working space harmless for health for employees.

Under this paper small field research will be assessed on Occupational health and safety in Georgia. Paper will show risks at the working place, physical and fatal at workplace, steps taken by Georgian government to eliminate risks or to mitigate and manage them and finally show current situation.

The article below discusses the steps and processes involved to make workplace safe and secure for employees and shows outcomes observing Georgian example. Will be discussed labor legislation changes according to HS field and OSHA and ILO standards taken as manual in Georgia.

Keywords: HSSE, Risk, Management, OSHA, ILO, Georgia

Occupational Safety and Health

Workplace safety is a shared responsibility of employee and employer, all individuals at the workplace have right to be safe and secure while working at the employer. This is the main case while signing official work contract. Occupational health and safety management keeps employer safe form negative aspects of job performed and employees and other people involved from life threatening, health and physical threats. Helps to create safe and secure space for work that under legislation and other management demands.

Job done by employee can be mental or physical but it should not be life and health threatening. Liability

and responsibility chain between employee and employer connect both very tight – employer should give secure and safe workplace to employee.

During 2011-2017 injuries and death at the workplace totaled 882 and 317. Georgian government started working on new legislation that would have protected employees form workplace deaths and injuries. Project was accepted by the government at march 7 2018.

Under the Labor Legislation occupational safety is major at the workplace. Government is obliged to support entities and support competitiveness. Georgian legislation also protects migrated Georgian citizens.

WORKPLACE DEATHS & INJURIES COMBINED BY YEAR

* 2022 data through September 30 only.

WORKPLACE DEATHS BY YEAR

* 2022 data through September 30 only.

All the inconveniences with the management inside the company of the occupational safety will be monitored and judges under the international HS manuals and ILO and OSHA manuals as well.

All the injuries and health or mental issues raised from workplace will be discussed by the labor code N997, that takes into account remuneration and compensation of injuries and health problems derived from workplace.

All the laws broken at the workplace will be disrespect of criminal procedure code and sanctions or more serious decisions will be taken from criminal code.

Unfortunately, this law is processed but obliges only for high risk jobs and workplaces and not every company operating in Georgia e.g construction, manufacturing mining transport etc.

TOP 5 SECTORS FOR DEATHS & INJURIES COMBINED (2019-22)

* 2022 data through September 2022 only

(shroma, 2022)

The main reason why labor safety was taken into consideration was 2015-2017 research that showed that from 583 companies checked from different fields (such as agriculture, retail, mining, construction, logistics, warehousing, etc.) none of them had fully safe and secure offices for their employees. Non of them had HSE (Health and Safety Executive), no against fire devices and no trainings what to do in different situations when health risks raise, most companies had poor sanitary and hygiene and there were no collective security systems.

After preparing and presenting changes in labor code, 19 trainings were taken about different up mentioned occupational security and safety procedures.

How workplace safety and security is monitored, assessed and managed worldwide

To identify workplace hazards, OSHA gives us clear instructions.

To identify and assess hazards, employers and workers:

- Collect and review information. This information can be present or likely be in future
- Conduct initial and periodic workplace inspections
- Investigate health damage cases determine causing hazards.
- Group similar incidents and identify trends in injuries.
- Consider nonregular hazards, that arise from emergency situations.
- Determine the severity and likelihood of incidents and prioritize corrective actions.

Companies start to inform employees on workplace hazards byboth internal and external sources. Both employers and employees collect, organize, and review information what type of hazards may be present and potentially exposed. they regularly inspect the workplace for hazards that help prevent an incident to occur, from the information they get by regular inspections of all operations, equipment, work areas and facilities. Workers, who directly work at hazardous place are main sources of information.

Documenting cases ar very important, later to inspect hazardous places make sure conditions are corrected. Photo/video evidence of problem should be taken for meetings how to control them, and for use as learning aids.

What is a risk assessment?

After identifying risks at the workplace risk assessments process occurs. In short, identifying what hazards currently exist or may appear in the workplace and are likely to cause harm to employees and visitors. Risks are/have to be considered at all employee occupied places. Workplace risk assessment process may include such hazards as: electrical and fire safety, manual handling, substances related, repetitive strain injury, stress, violence, diseases. When should risk assessment be done? Risk assessment should be ongoing process and it has to be done all the way down the working process.

How are risks ranked or prioritized?

Ranking hazards, in other words, determining priority to risks which to control first. Priority is given by examining employee vulnerability, potential for incident, damage or injury or illness. After raking risks action list is created.

There are several techniques to determine the level of risk. It is not easy and simple process. The organization determines most effective technique for them to work best for each situation. Ranking hazards requires good knowledge of all workplace activities including all operations with depth.

For the small and easy situations, an assessment can be a discussion or brainstorming session, based on past knowledge or similar situations. For the big companies, special team is working on hazard identification, documentation regulation and assessment. For them checklists or a probability matrix can be helpful.

RISK ASSESSMENT MATRIX				
SEVERITY \ PROBABILITY	Catastrophic (1)	Critical (2)	Marginal (3)	Negligible (4)
Frequent (A)	High	High	Serious	Medium
Probable (B)	High	High	Serious	Medium
Occasional (C)	High	Serious	Medium	Low
Remote (D)	Serious	Medium	Medium	Low
Improbable (E)	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low
Eliminated (F)	Eliminated			

(CPC, 2016)

Hazard Control

After risk ranking, the organization can decide on ways to control each specific hazard. A hazard control program is ways to protect workers from exposure to a substance or system, the training and the procedures required to monitor worker exposure and their health to hazards such as chemicals, materials or substance. General ways to control a hazard include Elimination (remove the hazard), Substitution (replace the hazard with a less hazardous one), Engineering Controls (includes plant redesigning, equipment, ventilation systems, and reduce exposure), Administrative Controls (controls how work is done), Personal Protective Equipment (equipment worn by individuals).

SUMMARY

After all, why is risk assessment and management so important?

Once I read an article in the journal that was starting like this : “The biggest work for the occupational safety and security progress was done by the dead employee who dies at the workplace..”

For the effective and efficient work process risk management is crucial. At some point it guarantees likeness of success, as if anything goes out of rails, managers are likely to have plan of corrective acts. Risk management is an important process because it empowers a business with the necessary tools so that it can adequately identify and deal with potential risks.

Risks can be divided based on the nature of their impact on your finances: income risk and expense risk.

Any events or mishaps that reduce your productivity – or your ability to provide services to your clients – will result in a loss of income.

Another positive impact of risk management is on your assets. You can avoid costly expenses that can arise due to damage or destruction of assets if you have precautions taken. Loss of critical assets can have a huge impact, especially if your business is an SME.

Unfortunately, yet in Georgia labor safety and security is not still leveling up but, companies started work on improving this field. There is hope in future that regular inspections will help to prioritize workplace security and safety of the company’s most valuable assets.

References:

1. CPC. (2016). <https://www.survival411.org/risk-matrix>. Retrieved from <https://www.survival411.org/risk-matrix>: <https://www.survival411.org/risk-matrix>
2. HSE. (2020). Health and Security Executive. Retrieved from Health and Security Executive: <https://www.hse.gov.uk/simple-health-safety/risk/index.htm>
3. OSHA. (2022). Occupational Safety and Health Administration. Retrieved from OSHA.gov: <https://www.osha.gov/safety-management/hazard-identification>
4. shroma. (2022). Retrieved from <https://shroma.ge/en/workplace-deaths-injuries-en/>